

6THCESUST2025: 6TH SYMPOSIUM ON CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY

PROGRAM AUTHORS KEYWORDS SLIDES

PROGRAM

Days: [Monday, June 16th](#) [Tuesday, June 17th](#)
[Wednesday, June 18th](#)

Monday, June 16th

View this program: [with abstracts](#) [session overview](#) [talk overview](#)

08:00-09:00 Session Registration: Registration

LOCATION: [Foyer Apollo](#)

09:00-09:30 Session OS: Opening Session

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

09:30-10:30 Session PS1: Plenary Session

CHAIR:

[Spyridon Ntougias](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

09:30 [Dimitrios Komilis](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

Current status and challenges in solid waste management globally: Are we in the correct path? ([abstract](#))

10:30-11:00 Session PN: Project-Network Session

CHAIR:

[Spyridon Ntougias](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

10:30 [Almudena Munoz-Puche](#) (Technological Centre of Furniture and Wood of the Region of Murcia, Spain)

[Vasiliki Skoulou](#) (University of Hull, UK)

[Aleksandar Ercerg](#) (J.J. Strossmayer University, Croatia)

[Hasan Volkan Oral](#) (Istanbul Aydin University, Turkey)

[Merim Kasumovic](#) (Tuzla University, Bosnia and Herzegovina)

[Jiri Strouhal](#) (Skoda Auto University, Czechia)

LIAISE COST ACTION: Leveraging Industrial Symbiosis as a Transformational Tool for Sustainable Industrial Practices ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Almudena Munoz-Puche](#)

10:45 [Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

From Industrial Symbiosis to Hubs for Circularity (IS2H4C) Project: A Review of Advancements ([abstract](#))

11:00-11:30 ☕ Coffee Break

Foyer Apollo

11:30-13:30 Session S1A: Circular Innovation and Design Part A

CHAIR:

[George Archimidis Tsalidis](#) (Imperial College London, UK)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

11:30 [Daniela Amorim](#) (Lepabe, Portugal)
[Fernando Martins](#) (Lepabe, Portugal)
[José Pires](#) (Lepabe, Portugal)

Double materiality assessment in industry and services and the connection with the environmental management system ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Daniela Amorim](#)

11:50 [Oscar Nieto-Cerezo](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)
[Dani Justel](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)
[Dorleta Ibarra](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)
[Joan Manuel F. Mendoza](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)

Dynamic Closed-Loop Circular Business Model for End-of-Life Wind Turbine Blade Management under Price Competition. ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Oscar Nieto-Cerezo](#)

12:10 [George Archimidis Tsalidis](#) (Imperial College London, UK)
[Pilar Brettes](#) (FUNDACION GAIKER, Spain)
[Daniel Dias](#) (Imperial College London, UK)
[Elena Koumaki](#) (Imperial College London, UK)
[Leire Ruiz](#) (University of the Basque Country, Spain)

[Evina Katsou](#) (Imperial College London, UK)

Environmental impacts and costs of soil bioremediation ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [George Archimidis Tsalidis](#)

12:30 [Ezgi Cevre](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Mert Güller](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Cemil Alpay Sunnetci](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)

Calculating and Managing the Carbon Footprint of Events: A Digital Approach with eventCO₂ ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Ezgi Cevre](#)

12:50 [Theoni I. Oikonomou](#) (Harokopio University & Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES), Greece)
[Spyridon Karytsas](#) (Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES), Greece)
[Ana Teresa Lima](#) (Technical University of Denmark, Denmark)
[Ioannis Kostakis](#) (Harokopio University, Greece)
[Constantine Karytsas](#) (Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES), Greece)
[Eleni Theodoropoulou](#) (Harokopio University, Greece)

Stakeholders' perceptions on circular economy in the construction sector: A case

study for Greece ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Theoni I. Oikonomou](#)

11:30-13:30 Session S1B: Circular Supply Chain Management

CHAIR:

[Konstantinos Giannakas](#) (University of Nebraska-Lincoln, United States)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

11:30 [Alicia Martinez de Yuso Ariza](#) (Zaragoza Logistics Center - ZLC, Spain)
[Beatriz Royo](#) (Zaragoza Logistics Center - ZLC, Spain)
[Sara Sanchez](#) (Zaragoza Logistics Center - ZLC, Spain)

A System Dynamics Framework for Circular Supply Chain Decision-Making in Carbonated Slags for Cement Production ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Alicia Martinez de Yuso Ariza](#)

11:50 [Beatriz Royo](#) (Zaragoza Logistics Center - ZLC, Spain)
[Alicia Martinez de Yuso](#) (Zaragoza Logistics Center - ZLC, Spain)
[Sara Sanchez](#) (Zaragoza Logistics Center - ZLC, Spain)

A System Dynamics Framework for Circular Supply Chain Decision-Making in the integration of Synthetic Natural Gas (SNG) ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Alicia Martinez de Yuso](#)

12:10 [Ahmed Chennak](#) (University of Nebraska-Lincoln, United States)
[Konstantinos Giannakas](#) (University of Nebraska-Lincoln, United States)
[Tala Awada](#) (Agricultural Research Division, University of Nebraska-Lincoln, United States)

Transitioning to more Circular Supply Chains: A Framework and Measures ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Konstantinos Giannakas](#)

12:30 [Aya Abdelmeguid](#) (University of Oxford, UK)
[Lucia Corsini](#) (University of Oxford, UK)

Systems Barriers, Enablers, and Leverage points in Circular Economy Transition for Electrical and Electronic Equipment Sector: Evidence from the UK ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Aya Abdelmeguid](#)

12:50 [Mert Güller](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Cemil Alpay Sünneci](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Ömer Oktay](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)

Carbon Footprint Analysis of Sultana Grapes in the Manisa Region ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Mert Güller](#)

13:10 [Deniz Uztürk](#) (Galatasaray University, Turkey)
[Gulcin Buyukozkan](#) (Galatasaray University, Turkey)

A Design-Oriented Decision-Making Framework for Circular Economy Integration in Agri-Food Supply Chains ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Deniz Uztürk](#)

13:30-14:30 || Lunch Break

Hotel Restaurant

14:30-16:30 Session S2A: Regional Circular Economy and Business Models

CHAIR:

[Inyene Nkanta](#) (University of West of Scotland, UK)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

14:30 [Gaby Gijsberts-Engstfeld](#) (ZUYD UAS, Maastricht, The Netherlands, Netherlands)
[Inyene Nkanta](#) (University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom, UK)
[Nikos Kalogeras](#) (University & Research (WUR), Wageningen, The Netherlands., Netherlands)

Driving Sustainability: Circular Economy Implementation in Hospitality SMEs in Limburg ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Inyene Nkanta](#)

14:50 [Olympia Polyzou](#) (CRES, Greece)
[Constantine Karytsas](#) (CRES, Greece)
[Theoni Oikonomou](#) (CRES, Greece)
[John Choropanitis](#) (CRES, Greece)

The project "Sorbent based processes for highly efficient and compact CO2 capture technologies"- SHEETS ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Constantine Karytsas](#)

15:10 [Savvas Papadopoulos](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Canan Acar](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Artur Pozarlik](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Circular Design of H2 Systems: The Case Study of Twente-Almelo Hub for Circularity ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Savvas Papadopoulos](#)

15:30 [Spyridon Karytsas](#) (Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES), Greece)
[Theoni I. Oikonomou](#) (Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES), Greece)
[Constantine Karytsas](#) (CRES, Greece)

Factors motivating residential renovations: Citizen-survey results from nine European countries ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Spyridon Karytsas](#)

15:50 [Amaryllis Mavragani](#) (Department of Economics, Universitat Jaume I, Castellon, Spain, Greece)
[Konstantinos Tsagarakis](#) (Technical University of Crete, Greece)

The Circular Economy millstone on water recycling reclamation and reuse literature ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Konstantinos Tsagarakis](#)

14:30-16:30 Session S2B: Education and Public Awareness

CHAIR: [Sermin Çakıcı Alp](#) (Hacettepe University, Turkey)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

14:30 [Sermin Çakıcı Alp](#) (Hacettepe University, Turkey)
[Meltem Yılmaz](#) (Hacettepe University, Turkey)
[Esra Özkan Yazgan](#) (Hacettepe University, Turkey)

The Creation Story of a Graduate Curriculum for Architectural Education Focused on Sustainability ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Sermin Çakıcı Alp](#)

14:50 [Stamatina Papadaki](#) (West Attica University, Greece)

Socioeconomic status and lifestyle behaviors on adolescent overweight in Greece: Implications for sustainable public health ([abstract](#))

15:10 [Elena Cristina Rada](#) (Insubria University, Italy)
[Anca Draghici](#) (Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania)
[Grazia Ragazzi](#) (Arcivescovile Insitute, Italy)
[Linda Allison](#) (Arcivescovile Insitute, Italy)
[Luca Adami](#) (University of Trento, Italy)

The role of plastic/packaging in the environmental sustainability education: an integrated example of vertical cooperation ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Elena Cristina Rada](#)

15:30 [Sofia Kondyli](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Spyridoula Bouliota](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Dimitrios Komilis](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

Evaluation of consumer behaviour on textile waste in Greece ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Sofia Kondyli](#)

15:50 [Kiriaki Keramitsoglou](#) (1st EPAL Didymoteichou "Evgenios Evgenidis", Leonidou 52-54, 68300 Didimoticho, Greece, Greece)

[Carolina Iakovidou](#) (1st EPAL Didymoteichou "Evgenios Evgenidis", Leonidou 52-54, 68300 Didimoticho, Greece, Greece)

[Domna Konstantinidou](#) (1st EPAL Didymoteichou "Evgenios Evgenidis", Leonidou 52-54, 68300 Didimoticho, Greece, Greece)

[Dimitra Tasidou](#) (1st EPAL Didymoteichou "Evgenios Evgenidis", Leonidou 52-54, 68300 Didimoticho, Greece, Greece)

An innovative food packaging inspired by the tradition ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Kiriaki Keramitsoglou](#)

16:10 [George Tsalidis](#) (Imperial College London, UK)

[Andreas Kyriakidis](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)

[Ioannis Ioannou](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)

[Apostolos Michopoulos](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)

Carbon benefits of employing waste material in the construction industry of Cyprus ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [George Tsalidis](#)

CHAIR:

[Frank Stevens](#) (Technical University of Crete, Netherlands)

LOCATION: [Lefkipos](#)

14:30 [Idiano D'Adamo](#) (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)
[Simona Desideri](#) (Independent Researcher, Italy)
[Martina Iannilli](#) (Independent Researcher, Italy)
Altruism: the true frontier of sustainability. Results from the Digital Product Passport analysis ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Idiano D'Adamo](#)

14:45 [Idiano D'Adamo](#) (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)
[Chiara Grosso](#) (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)
[Roberta Palmieri](#) (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)
Made in Italy, Circular Economy and Digital Product Passport: A business perspective ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Idiano D'Adamo](#)

15:00 [Paolo Basilico](#) (Independent Researcher, Italy)
[Idiano D'Adamo](#) (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)
[Federica Di Santo](#) (Independent Researcher, Italy)
[Massimo Gastaldi](#) (University of L'Aquila, Italy)
Renewable energy communities: concern and information towards sustainability ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Massimo Gastaldi](#)

15:15 [Paraskevi Angeletopoulou](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[Ioannis Kostakis](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[Eleni Sardianou](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[Dimitrios Damigos](#) (Technical University of Athens, Greece)
[Roido Mitoula](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[George Malindretos](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[Stamatina Papadaki](#) (University of West Attica, Greece)
[Giacomo Di Foggia](#) (University of Milano – Bicocca, Italy)
[Massimo Beccarello](#) (University of Milano – Bicocca, Italy)
Comparative analysis of energy poverty in Greece and Italy: Regional disparities and policy implications ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Roido Mitoula](#)

15:30 [Roido Mitoula](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[Maria Briana](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)
[Eleni Sardianou](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)

Digital City Branding and Smart Urban Governance: A Citizen-Centered Analysis
([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Roido Mitoula](#)

15:45 [Michalis Christodoulou](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)

Zr⁴⁺ MOFs and MOF Composites as Sorbents for the Removal of Selected Pharmaceuticals
([abstract](#))

16:30-17:00 ☕ Coffee Break

Foyer Apollo

17:00-18:40 Session S3A: Circular Innovation and Design Part B

CHAIR:

[Kai Rommel](#) (International School of Management Dortmund, Germany)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

17:00 [Kai Rommel](#) (International School of Management Dortmund, Germany)

[Marius Linden](#) (International School of Management Cologne, Germany)

[Jens Perret](#) (International School of Management Cologne, Germany)

[Andreas Helferich](#) (International School of Management Stuttgart, Germany)

Sustainable Web-design: Digital Marketing Potentials ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Kai Rommel](#)

17:20 [Kestutis Lekeckas](#) (VDA, KTU, Lithuania)

Systemic Fashion Design: Morphological Tools for Sustainable Development ([abstract](#))

17:40 [Georgia Kotsari](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

[Christos Baloutsos](#) (Intramek, Greece)

The Impact of Autonomous Machinery and Robotics in Smart Agriculture: Case Study
([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Georgia Kotsari](#)

18:00 [Damyan Fasulkov](#) (Zuyd UAS, Netherlands)

[Nikolaos Kalogeras](#) (Zuyd & Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands)

Dual-LLM Architecture for Real-Time EU Sustainability Compliance Analysis: Bridging Regulatory Theory and Corporate Performance ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Damyan Fasulkov](#)

17:00-18:40 Session S3B: Sustainable Production and Circularity

CHAIR: [Canan Acar](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

17:00 [Canan Acar](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Advancing Circularity: Hydrogen's Role in Sustainable Energy ([abstract](#))

17:20 [Su Kunt](#) (METU, Turkey)

[Metin U. Salamci](#) (Gazi University, Turkey)

[Mehmet Kabak](#) (Gazi University, Turkey)

[Emre Alp](#) (METU, Turkey)

Environmental Performance Assessment of Metal Additive Manufacturing Processes

([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Emre Alp](#)

17:40 [Triantafyllia Karampini](#) (PhD Candidate, Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)
[Georgios Tsironis](#) (Post Doc Researcher, School of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, Chania, Greece, Greece)

[Evaggelos Drimpetas](#) (Professor, Department of Economics, DUTH Greece, Greece)

[Konstantinos P. Tsagarakis](#) (Professor School of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, Chania, Greece, Greece)

LinkedIn-Based Trend Analysis of Circular Economy Companies in the Nordic Region: Insights from Organizational Profiles and Social Engagement Metrics ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Triantafyllia Karampini](#)

18:00 [Malahat Ghoreishi](#) (LAB University of Applied Sciences, Finland)

Value chain mapping of the wastewater and residual sludge treatment for circular economy ([abstract](#))

18:20 [Dimitra Matziri](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Nikolaos Remmas](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Paraschos Melidis](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Spyridon Ntougias](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

Valorization Potential of Photosynthetic Microorganisms towards a Bio-Based Circular Economy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Dimitra Matziri](#)

20:00-23:00 Gala Dinner

Next to the Hotel swimming pool

Tuesday, June 17th

View this program: [with abstracts](#) [session overview](#) [talk overview](#)

09:00-10:00 Session WKSEP: Workshop "Ethics in Publishing"

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

09:00 [Amaryllis Mavragani](#) (LLE & Department of Economics, Universitat Jaume I, Spain)

[Tiffany Leung](#) (JMIR Publications, Canada)

[Aurora García-Gallego](#) (LLE & Department of Economics, Universitat Jaume I, Spain)

[Nikolaos Georgantzis](#) (Burgundy School of Business, France)

Ethics in Research and Publishing: Author- and Reviewer- Perspective ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Amaryllis Mavragani](#)

10:00-11:00 Session PL3: Plenary Session

CHAIR:

[Spyridon Rapsomanikis](#) (Unit of ENvironmental processes Technologies and Applications (ENTA), Athena RC, Greece)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

10:00 [Mark Jolly](#) (Cranfield University, UK)

Transforming the materials agenda for a sustainable planet: Opportunities and challenges ([abstract](#))

11:00-11:30 ☕ Coffee Break

Foyer Apollo

11:30-13:30 Session S4A: Circular Materials and Product Flows

CHAIR:

[Bruno Damasio](#) (NOVA Information Management School (NOVA IMS), Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal, Portugal)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

11:30 [Anna M. Hansson](#) (School of Business, Innovation and Sustainability, Halmstad University, Sweden)

[Niklas P.E. Karlsson](#) (School of Business, Innovation and Sustainability, Halmstad University, Sweden)

[Jeaneth Johansson](#) (Halmstad University/Luleå University of Technology, Sweden)

[Marie Mattsson](#) (School of Business, Innovation and Sustainability, Halmstad University, Sweden)

[Desirée Gran](#) (IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, Sweden)

[Nina Chi Johansson](#) (IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, Sweden)

[Anders Hjort](#) (IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, Sweden)

[Sofia Klugman](#) (IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, Sweden)

[Henrik Andersson](#) (School of Business, Innovation and Sustainability, Halmstad University, Sweden)

Drivers and barriers for adopting and implementing biogas-based industrial symbiosis in Sweden ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Anna M. Hansson](#)

11:50 [Joana Gonçalves](#) (NOVA Information Management School (NOVA IMS), Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal, Portugal)

[Bruno Damasio](#) (NOVA Information Management School (NOVA IMS), Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal, Portugal)

[José Silva](#) (Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal, Portugal)

[Sandro Mendonça](#) (Business Research Unit (BRU-IUL), University Institute of Lisbon (ISCTE-IUL), Lisboa, Portugal, Portugal)

Closing the Solar Loop: Sustainability Trends in Photovoltaic Research ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Bruno Damasio](#)

12:10 [Akrivi Korba](#) (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece)

[Lucyna Lekawska-Andrinopoulou](#) (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece)

[Kostas Chatziioannou](#) (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece)

[Georgios Tsimiklis](#) (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece)

[Angelos Amditis](#) (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece)

Material Flow Analysis for Construction and Demolition Waste Management: A Use Case at a Construction Site in Greece ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Akrivi Korba](#)

12:30 [Ana Outeirinho Morgado](#) (Circular Economy and Sustainability Lab, University of Oxford, UK)

[Lucia Corsini](#) (Circular Economy and Sustainability Lab, University of Oxford, UK)

Mapping Flows of Electrical and Electronic Equipment to enable a Circular Economy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Ana Outeirinho Morgado](#)

12:50 [Marco Ragazzi](#) (University of Trento, Italy)

[Gianni Andreottola](#) (University of Trento, Italy)

[Luca Adami](#) (University of Trento, Italy)

Potentialities and criticalities of in-field tests for soil improvement by residual biomass from enhanced thermal treatments ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Marco Ragazzi](#)

13:10 [George Tsironis](#) (School of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, 73100 Chania, Greece, Greece)

[Panagiotis Zikos](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Stathis Vlachos](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Vasileios Douvris](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Georgios Angelopoulos](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Nikos Rozis](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Panagiota Theodoridou](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Evangelos Kitsoulis](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

Blockchain-Enabled Traceability and Just-In-Time Logistics for Sustainable AgriFood Supply Chains in the COP-PILOT EU Project ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Georgios Angelopoulos](#)

Hubs for Circularity

Co-organized with the Sustainable Circular Economy Transition: from Industrial Symbiosis to Hubs for Circularity – IS2H4C

CHAIR:

[Antonios Konstantas](#) (European Institutions - HaDEA, Belgium)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

- 11:30 [Alessio Trivella](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Jiayun Wang](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Tobias Nielsen](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Daniela Guericke](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Devrim M. Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Optimizing the Design and Operation of Hubs for Circularity using Quantitative Analytics and Operations Research ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Alessio Trivella](#)

- 11:50 [Yifei Yu](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Agent-Based Modelling for Hubs for Circularity: A Conceptual Framework ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Yifei Yu](#)

- 12:10 [Elif Erdiñç Arca](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Yifei Yu](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Devrim Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Circular Carbon Economy: A Review and Technology Projections for Carbon-based Industrial Symbiosis ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Elif Erdiñç Arca](#)

- 12:30 [Aidana Tleuken](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Patricia Rogetzer](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Luca Fraccascia](#) (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)
[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Analyzing Organizational and Resource Flow Networks for Hubs for Circularity: A Social Network Analysis Approach ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Patricia Rogetzer](#)

- 12:50 [Hisham Afash](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Mila Koeva](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Yifei Yu](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)
[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Advancing Hubs for Circularity Through Digital Twin Technology: An Analysis of Quantifying Performance Indicators ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Hisham Afash](#)

- 13:10 [Antonios Konstantas](#) (European Institutions -

HaDEA, Belgium)

EU Environmental actions and the concept of Industrial Symbiosis ([abstract](#))

13:30-14:30 || Lunch Break

Hotel Restaurant

14:30-16:30 Session S5A: Accelerating Circular Transitions: LIAISE COST Action members' contributors to Industrial Symbiosis and Sustainable Innovation

CHAIR:

[Almudena Muñoz](#) (Technological Centre of Furniture and Wood of the Region of Murcia, Spain)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

- 14:30 [Almudena Muñoz](#) (Technological Centre of Furniture and Wood of the Region of Murcia, Spain)
[Juan José Ortega Gras](#) (Technological Centre of Furniture and Wood of the Region of Murcia, Spain)
[Samira Khemkhen](#) (Strasbourg University, France)
[Funda Kerbriand](#) (Strasbourg University Web, France)

Closing the Gap: Overcoming Challenges in Industrial Symbiosis Implementation – Lessons from the INSET Project ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Almudena Muñoz](#)

- 14:50 [Apostolos Michopoulos](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)
[Vicky Skoulou](#) (University of Hull, UK)

Accelerating Industrial Symbiosis schemes: Lessons learned from indicative cases studies ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Apostolos Michopoulos](#)

- 15:10 [Daniela Amorim](#) (KPMG, Portugal)
[Renato Monteiro](#) (KPMG, Portugal)
[Catarina Velhas](#) (KPMG, Portugal)
[João Torres](#) (KPMG, Portugal)
[Miguel Monteiro](#) (KPMG, Portugal)

The study of externalities in a business model based on the circular economy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Daniela Amorim](#)

- 15:30 [Ana Ramos](#) (INEGI - Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Portugal)

Advancing Industrial Symbiosis through Targeted Training: A Research and Technology Organization's Perspective ([abstract](#))

- 15:50 [Oscar Nieto-Cerezo](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)
[Dani Justel](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)
[Dorleta Ibarra](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)
[Joan Manuel F. Mendoza](#) (Mondragon University, Spain)

Agent-based Modelling for the End-of-Life Management of Wind Turbine Blades: Integrating Economic and Environmental Impacts ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Oscar Nieto-Cerezo](#)

- 16:10 [Nicolas Labra Cataldo](#) (The University of Manchester, UK)
[Alejandro Gallego Schmid](#) (The University of Manchester, UK)
[Ben Parkes](#) (The University of Manchester, UK)
[Caterina Doglioni](#) (The University of Manchester, UK)
[Tobias Fitschen](#) (The University of Manchester, UK)

Tackling the Energetic Cost and Resource Consumption of Research Computing: A Life Cycle Perspective on Hardware and Software Efficiency at the University of Manchester
([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nicolas Labra Cataldo](#)

14:30-16:30 Session S5B: Sustainable Economic Growth

CHAIR: [Hairong Mu](#) (Harper Adams University, UK)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

- 14:30 [Stepan Vorobets](#) (Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine)
[Viktoriya Voytsekhovska](#) (Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine)
[Orest Koleshchuk](#) (Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine)
[Olena Zahoretska](#) (Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine)

Food (in)Security and Russian military aggression in Ukraine across SDG.2: case study for main crops. ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Viktoriya Voytsekhovska](#)

- 14:50 [Hairong Mu](#) (Harper Adams University, UK)
[Jing Sun](#) (Qingdao University of China, China)
[Mengfei Li](#) (Qingdao University of China, China)
The Path to Breaking the Impasse of Marine Negative Emission Economy: Empirical Study of the Multi-Dimensional Spillover Effects of Blue Carbon Fisheries ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Hairong Mu](#)

- 15:10 [Burcu Yildirim](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Mert Güller](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Cemil Alpay Sunnetci](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)
[Saki Onur Dalgic](#) (<https://www.3pmetrics.com/>, Turkey)

Carbon and Water Footprint Assessment in the Tourism Sector: An Applied Approach Based on ISO 14064-1, ISO 14046, and GHG Protocol for Four Hotels ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Burcu Yildirim](#)

- 15:30 [Anastasia Kyriakidou](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)
[Maria Tsiouni](#) (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece)
[Dimitrios Papadas](#) (Harper Adams University, UK)
[Aristotelis Batzios](#) (International Hellenic

University, Greece)
[Aristea Kounani](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

The Effects of Gross Domestic Product and Renewable Energy Consumption on Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Emissions: Evidence from an ARDL Bounds Test Approach for Greece.

([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Maria Tsiouni](#)

15:50 [Georgios Tsironis](#) (School of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, 73100 Chania, Greece, Greece)

[Panagiotis Zikos](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Stathis Vlachos](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Vasileios Douvris](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

[Georgios Angelopoulos](#) (iLINK New Technologies, Greece)

ENVISION: AI-Enhanced UAV Analytics for Sustainable Land and Forest Management in the CHAMELEON EU Project ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Georgios Angelopoulos](#)

16:10 [Dimitrios Papadas](#) (HARPER ADAMS UNIVERSITY, Greece)

[Nur Catana](#) (Coca-Cola Turkey, Turkey)

Exploring the Nexus Between Economic Growth, CO₂ Emissions, and Climate Resilience in the Context of Circular Economy: Comparative Evidence from Greece and Turkey ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nur Catana](#)

16:30-17:00 ☕ Coffee Break

Foyer Apollo

17:00-19:00 Session S6A: Energy, Biogas and Circularity

CHAIR:

[Ana Ramos](#) (INEGI - Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Portugal)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

17:00 [Dimitrios Dimitriou](#) (MaGBISE Research Laboratory, Department of Economics, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Aristi Karagkouni](#) (MaGBISE Research Laboratory, Department of Economics, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

Circular Economy as Strategy: The Role of Supply Chain Analytics in Corporate Performance Evaluation ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Aristi Karagkouni](#)

17:20 [Evgenia Politou](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Konstantinos Azis](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Anastasia Makri](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Nikolaos Remmas](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Spyridon Ntougias](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Paraschos Melidis](#) (Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

AnMBR as a Circular Wastewater Treatment Solution: Performance, Cost Analysis, and Energy Recovery ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Evgenia Politou](#)

17:40 [Dimitrios Dimitriou](#) (MaGBISE Research Laboratory, Department of Economics, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Maria Sartzetaki](#) (MaGBISE Research Laboratory, Department of Economics, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Antonia Moutzouri](#) (Department of Economics, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

Methodological Framework to Evaluate Airport Corporate Ethical Stigma towards Sustainability ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Dimitrios Dimitriou](#)

18:00 [Gözde Özbayram](#) (Istanbul University, Turkey)

[Latife Köker](#) (Istanbul University, Turkey)

[Reyhan Akçaalan](#) (Istanbul University, Turkey)

[Meriç Albay](#) (Istanbul University, Turkey)

Potential of Macrophytes for Sustainable Biogas Production in a Circular Bioeconomy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Gözde Özbayram](#)

18:20 [Aristea Kounani](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

[Maria Tsiouni](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

[Alexandra Pavloudi](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

[Achilleas Kontogeorgos](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

Environmental Economics: Assessment of the Economic Efficiency of Circularity Practices in Olive Oil Mills ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Aristea Kounani](#)

18:40 [Ana Ramos](#) (INEGI - Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Portugal)

Life Cycle Assessment of Electricity Generation from Biomass: A Comparative Analysis of Combustion and Gasification Pathways ([abstract](#))

17:00-19:00 Session S6B: Sustainable Economic Growth and Development

CHAIR:

[George Archimidis Tsalidis](#) (Imperial College London, UK)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

17:00 [Dimitrios Dimitriou](#) (University of West Attica, Department of Accounting and Finance, Greece)

[Ioannis Kostakis](#) (Harokopio University of Athens, Greece)

[Alexandros Tsioutsios](#) (Department of

Economics, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece)

The Ecological Footprint of G-7 Countries: An Artificial Intelligence Approach ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Dimitrios Dimitriou](#)

- 17:20 [Alessandro Russo](#) (University of Sannio, Italy)
[Dimitra Papadaki](#) (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece)
[Silvia Ruggiero](#) (University of Sannio, Italy)
[Francesca Rosa De Masi](#) (University of Sannio, Italy)
[Margarita Niki Assimakopoulos](#) (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece)
[Gasper Stegnar](#) (Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia)

Building Archetypes for a Circular Economy: Integrating Stock Modelling, Material Flows, and Renovation Strategies ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Dimitra Papadaki](#)

- 17:40 [Iliana Kolari](#) (PhD Candidate, Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)
[Maria Sartzetaki](#) (Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)
[Dimitrios Dimitriou](#) (Professor, Head of the Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)

Integrating Circular Economy through Sustainable Corporate Culture and Human Resource Management ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Iliana Kolari](#)

- 18:00 [Dimitris Kenourgios](#) (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece)
[Alexandros Tsioutsios](#) (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece)

Alternative Assets in Times of Crisis: Hedging Potential and Safe Haven Dynamics ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Alexandros Tsioutsios](#)

- 18:20 [Konstantinos Pantelis](#) (University of Cyprus, Greece)

Towards the Construction of “Real World” Wastewater filters based on Zr⁴⁺ Metal Organic Framework Materials ([abstract](#))

- 18:40 [Triantafyllia Karampini](#) (DUTH, Greece)
[Aristi Karagkouni](#) (Adjusted Lecturer, Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)
[Evaggelos Drimpetas](#) (Professor, Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)
[Dimitrios Dimitriou](#) (Professor, Head of the Department of Economics, DUTH, Greece)

Circular Economy and Corporate Performance in Airport Operators: A Comparative Evaluation of EU and U.S. Practices ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Aristi Karagkouni](#)

Wednesday, June 18th

View this program: [with abstracts](#) [session overview](#) [talk overview](#)

09:00-11:00 Session S7A: Waste Management and Sustainable Recommendation Systems

CHAIR:

[Giacomo Di Foggia](#) (University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

09:00 [Abdulrasaq Ajadi Ishola](#) (Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria, Nigeria)

[Inyene Nkanta](#) (University of the West of Scotland, UK)

[Tokunbo Alaga Olorundami](#) (York St John University, UK)

Sustainable Waste Management practices in Stockholm and Lagos: Opportunities for possible framework transfer ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Inyene Nkanta](#)

09:20 [Ioannis Stavrakakis](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Paraschos Melidis](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

[Spyridon Ntougias](#) (Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece)

Solid-State Fermentation for Sustainable Waste Management and Valorisation of Orange Processing Waste as a Biotechnological Approach toward the Bioeconomy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Ioannis Stavrakakis](#)

09:40 [Victor Ramos](#) (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain)

[Konstantinos N. Pantelis](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)

[Eleni Hadjikyprianou](#) (University of Cyprus, Cyprus)

Iron-Based MOFs and MOF Composites for Sustainable Wastewater Treatment in the Circular Economy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Victor Ramos](#)

10:00 [Giacomo Di Foggia](#) (University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy)

[Ugo Arrigo](#) (University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy)

[Massimo Beccarello](#) (University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy)

The economic governance of urban waste management: objectives, tools and results ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Giacomo Di Foggia](#)

10:20 [Sinem Halli](#) (Industrial Design, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Türkiye, Turkey)

[Cigdem Kaya](#) (Industrial Design, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Türkiye, Turkey)

[Behcet Ugur Toreyin](#) (Informatics Institute, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Türkiye, Turkey)

Developing a Sustainability-Oriented Toy Recommendation System for Preschool Toys: A Multi-Layered Design Research Approach ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Sinem Halli](#)

CHAIR:

[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

09:00 [Arjun Chaudhuri](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Mahak Sharma](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Devrim Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Assessing Managerial Capabilities for Industry 4.0-Driven Food Supply Chains ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Arjun Chaudhuri](#)

09:20 [Haritha Mutharasu](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Patricia Rogetzer](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Marcos Machado](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Devrim Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Enhancing Circular Economy in Consumer Electronics: Data-Driven Strategies for Improving E-Commerce Returns ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Marcos Machado](#)

09:40 [Kaiyu Xie](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Marcos Machado](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Laura Spierdijk](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Devrim Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Understanding Supply Disruptions in Critical Raw Materials for Electric Vehicles: Causes, Patterns, and Implications ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Kaiyu Xie](#)

10:00 [Aditya Tripathi](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Marcos R. Machado](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Laura Spierdijk](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Devrim M. Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Valuing circularity for mainstream funding: A Machine Learning approach from single-firm initiatives to scalable Hubs for Circularity ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Aditya Tripathi](#)

10:20 [Muhammad Yasir Muzayan Haq](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Ghusen Chalan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Abhishta Abhishta](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Decision Support Tool for Cloud Service Selection in Industrial Symbiosis ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Muhammad Yasir Muzayan Haq](#)

10:40 [Alessandro Neri](#) (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy)

[Alessio Trivella](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

[Maria Angela Butturi](#) (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy)

[Devrim Murat Yazan](#) (University of Twente, Netherlands)

Quantifying the impact of battery repurposing and recycling in the EU's electric vehicle transition: a system dynamics modelling approach ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Alessandro Neri](#)

11:00-11:30 ☕ Coffee Break

Foyer Apollo

11:30-13:10 Session S8A: Sustainable Production and Consumption

CHAIR:

[Frank Stevens](#) (Technical University of Crete, Netherlands)

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

11:30 [Siegfried Eisele](#) (Technical University of Applied Sciences Augsburg, Germany)

[Frank Danzinger](#) (Technical University of Applied Sciences Augsburg, Germany)

[Peter Richard](#) (Technical University of Applied Sciences Augsburg, Germany)

Rebalancing perspectives: Smart remanufacturing and the overlooked importance of ERP systems ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Siegfried Eisele](#)

11:50 [Minje Choi](#) (Department of land economy, University of Cambridge, South Korea)

[Jaeyoung Chang](#) (Department of Transportation Engineering, University of Seoul, South Korea)

[Serin Min](#) (Department of Smart City, University of Seoul, South Korea)

[Sion Kim](#) (Department of Transportation Engineering, University of Seoul, South Korea)

[Juhyeon Kwak](#) (Department of Transportation Engineering, University of Seoul, South Korea)

[Seungjae Lee](#) (Department of Transportation Engineering, University of Seoul, South Korea)

Enhancing Urban Sustainability through Integrated Micro-Mobility Infrastructure: Policy and Practical Implications ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Minje Choi](#)

12:10 [Aristotelis Batzios](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

[Sotiria Baziana](#) (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece)

[Maria Tsiouni](#) (International Hellenic University, Greece)

[Ourania Tremma](#) (University College Dublin, Ireland)

COOPERATIVE IDENTITY AND BRANDING INFLUENCE ON FRESH FOOD MARKET: A MARKET EXPERTS' AND CONSUMERS'

OPINION STUDY IN THESSALONIKI REGION

([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Sotiria Baziana](#)

- 12:30 [Frank Stevens](#) (School of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, Chania, Greece, Netherlands)
[Konstantinos Tsagarakis](#) (School of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, Chania, Greece, Greece)

Circular Economy and Building Materials from an archaeological perspective: insights from the Netherlands and Greece since the Roman times. ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Frank Stevens](#)

11:30-13:10 Session S8B: Sustainable Productivity and Circular Economy

CHAIR: [Latife Köker](#) (Istanbul University, Turkey)

LOCATION: [Orfeas](#)

- 11:30 [Myrto Tsiknia](#) (Department of Natural Resources and Agricultural Engineering, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece)
[Nikolaos Paranychanakis](#) (School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Greece)

Dynamics of Microbial Community Assembly in Constructed Wetlands: Successional patterns and Ecological Stability ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Myrto Tsiknia](#)

- 11:50 [Viktor Kouloumpis](#) (Joint Research Centre - European Commission, Italy)
[Vincenzo Senatore](#) (European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Spain)
[Mattia Costamagna](#) (Project HUB 360, Italy)
[Anandu Syrus](#) (SCAI Tecno SPA, Italy)
[Paola Federica Albizzati](#) (European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Spain)
[Massimo Perucca](#) (Project HUB 360, Italy)
[Fulvio Ardente](#) (European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Italy)

Achieving durability in the textile sector ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Viktor Kouloumpis](#)

- 12:10 [Latife Köker](#) (Istanbul University, Faculty of Aquatic Sciences, Turkey)
[Gözde Özbayram](#) (Istanbul University, Turkey)
[Reyhan Akçaalan](#) (Istanbul University, Faculty of Aquatic Sciences, Turkey)
[Meriç Albay](#) (Istanbul University, Faculty of Aquatic Sciences, Turkey)

The Role of Aquatic Plants in Circular Economy Strategies ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Latife Köker](#)

- 12:30 [Myrto Paraschou](#) (Department of Agricultural Economics, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, Greece)
[Nikos Kalogeras](#) (Zuyd University of Applied Sciences & Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands, Netherlands)
[Panagiota Sergaki](#) (Department of Agricultural

Economics, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, Greece)
[Stefanos A. Nastis](#) (Department of Agricultural Economics, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, Greece)
[Anastasios Michailidis](#) (Department of Agricultural Economics, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, Greece)

Compulsory Membership and ESG Sustainability in Cooperatives: The case of Chios Mastic Growers ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Myrto Paraschou](#)

12:50 [Myrto Tsiknia](#) (Department of Natural Resources and Agricultural Engineering, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece)

[Georgios Leventis](#) (Department of Natural Resources and Agricultural Engineering, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece)

[Dimitra Stathopoulou](#) (Department of Natural Resources and Agricultural Engineering, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece)

[Antonios Apostolakis](#) (Department of Crop Sciences, University of Göttingen, Göttingen, Germany, Germany)

[Cleopatra Gareizou](#) (Department of Rehabilitation, Imerys Greece SA, Greece)

[Georgios Petrakis](#) (Department of Rehabilitation, Imerys Greece SA, Greece)

[Ehaliotis Constantinos](#) (Department of Natural Resources and Agricultural Engineering, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece)

Sustainable rehabilitation of quarries in Milos island: enhancement of indigenous plant community re-installation through integration of novel, microbiome-based restoration technologies. ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Myrto Tsiknia](#)

13:15-13:30 Session CS: Closing Session

LOCATION: [Dimokritos 1](#)

14:00-15:00 || Lunch Break

Hotel Restaurant

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